

A Geolocation-Integrated Emergency Blood Donation Response System (GI-BDERS)

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Abstract

This study develops and evaluates a geolocation-integrated emergency blood donation response system (GI-BDERS) to enhance operational efficiency in emergency blood donation processes in Nigeria. By employing descriptive analytics methodologies, the system provides actionable insights into response times, donor engagement, and matching accuracy. The integration of geolocation technologies, SMS notifications, and a robust database enables prompt and accurate donor-recipient matching. Designed using an agile methodology, it incorporates a secure database, blood compatibility guidelines, the Termii API for alerts, and the Google Maps API for location tracking.

Real-world tests yielded significant results, such as response rates for rare blood types reaching 57% and average reaction times ranging between 7 to 19 minutes across scenarios. Descriptive analytics methods were employed to collect and analyze data on response times, donor engagement, and matching accuracy. These findings demonstrate how GI-BDERS improves donor-recipient matching and reduces delays, enhancing emergency healthcare services. GI-BDERS demonstrates its potential to transform healthcare operations, with future work suggesting the integration of machine learning for predictive analytics to optimize emergency responses further.

Keywords: Blood Donation System, Blood Type compatibility, Blood Donor matching, Descriptive Analytics, Emergency Response Optimization, Geolocation Technology, Healthcare Analytics, Prescriptive Analytics, Web-based Application.

1.0 Introduction

Blood is a vital and special fluid that is only available through blood donation in cases of emergency or when an external supply is needed. Blood is a lifesaver for all living creatures [1]. Donating blood is a vital part of healthcare, and as blood can only be received from blood donors, it is a very special and valuable resource. Although many people are saved each year by donors, other people continue to suffer or die as a result of not having access to safe blood transfusions[2].

The world is currently dependent on technology, and people of all ages appear to be highly engaged in it. Due to its rapid advancement, technology has become a crucial part of life today and an essential part of modern society. Location tracking is one of the technologies of today. In today's world, a tracking system is a reliable and well-established innovation in technology [3]. It locates a target's current location, which could be a person, a car, or an object in a manufacturing facility. Geolocation systems play an important role in blood donation emergencies, its bridge the gap between the immediate need for blood and the potential donors who can provide it.

The study aims to implement a geolocation-integrated blood donation emergency response system with a specific focus on enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of blood donation processes in Nigeria. This study developed a web-based application system with a scalable and robust database that will be design for storage of the user information. Also, Google Maps was used to track the location of the emergency or where a blood donor is needed. SMS notifications was utilized to notify the donor of the emergency in this study.

1.1 Problem of Statement

In emergencies, locating compatible donors promptly is challenging, especially for rare blood types. Issues such as communication barriers, inadequate infrastructure for blood storage, and the lack of real-time tracking exacerbate the problem. GI-BDERS addresses these challenges by ensuring:

- Reliable donor-recipient communication.
- Real-time location tracking for emergencies.
- Efficient matching of blood types based on compatibility rules.

1.2 Geolocation Technology in Healthcare

Nowadays, a lot of apps that use geolocation have been created in accordance with the problem's context and system development goals in order to increase an application's added value [5]. Prior studies have created a geolocation-based heart rate monitoring app for Android that uses notifications like SMS and email to convey messages in the form of warning sounds. Real-time patient health monitoring is possible with geolocation technology [6]. An Android-based heart rate monitoring application that uses geolocation technology has been created by prior research. It sends alert noises via email and SMS alerts. GI-BDERS builds on these insights to provide a comprehensive solution for emergency blood donation.

2.0 Literature review

[1] employed incremental development lifecycle to developed Blood Bank Donor System which was capable of synchronizing communication between blood donors, recipients, hospitals, and/or blood banks. The application also allows registered users to access requests for blood, search for nearby hospitals/blood banks, and locate nearby donors.

Mobile-based Application was built on Android Studio platform for user to easy search for donor and get their contact details, including their location. The application enable users to communicate with donors directly through calls and messages in order to avoid miscommunication[7].

[8] discusses the development of a blood donor management system using mobile crowdsourcing. Its aims to make it easier for individuals in need of blood to find donors in their nearby location[8]. The system utilizes GPS technology to track the location of donors and allows users to search for donors based on their blood group.

[9] presents a framework for the development of an Android mobile application that facilitate blood services between blood and organ banks, blood/organ donors and blood/organ requesters. The interface was designed using android studio and MySQL server was used as database for data storage [9].

The B-Door app was created to protect the donor's privacy and donor identity, as well as the recipient's safety, using the J48 decision tree algorithm [10]. The Application was developed through Android Studio and Flutter UI Framework together with base at backside and provides our result on Real time basis [10]. [11] design and methodology cover system architecture use case diagram and uml diagram. The system architecture comprises of the main architecture in which we have a user application to which other entities are sending and receiving data. It features a firebase cloud messaging, a firebase database, and asp.net web services.

The Gaps and weakness that are identified from the previous research work of other researchers are Security issues, some researchers do not mention any specific security measures or protocols to protect the privacy of users' personal and medical information. Most of the researches does not consider the compatibility of the blood types of donors and recipient, which can lead to wasting of time when there is emergency need of the blood. Lack of real time location tracking of both the donor and recipient which is very important when it comes to emergency need of blood.

3.0 Methodology

This section outlines the methodology employed in this research, which aimed to design and implement a Web-based application that integrate Geolocation to Enhanced Blood Donation Emergency Response. Agile methodology was employed for the implementation of **GI-BDERS**.

3.1 Design a blood type compatibility rule for accurate matching.

To guarantee precise matching during blood transfusions, the information must be properly organized and represented in a structured manner for blood type compatibility regulations. ABO system and RH factor must be carefully considered for matching the donor and the recipient. Table 3.1 below gives an illustration of blood type, Rh factor, and their compatibility.

Table 3. 1: Blood Type and their Compatibility

Blood Type	Rh factor	Can donate to	Can receive from
A	A+	A+, AB+	A+, A-, O+, O-
	A-	A+, A-, AB+, AB-	O-, A-
B	B+	B+, AB+	B+, B-, O+, O-
	B-	B+, B-, AB+, AB-	B-, O-
AB	AB+	AB+	All blood type (Universal recipient)
	AB-	AB-, AB+	AB-, A-, B-, O-
O	O+	O+, A+, B+, AB+	O-, O+
	O-	All blood type (Universal donor)	O-

To give an accurate blood type compatibility, compatibility matrix will be created using Python. In this section, the blood compatibility rules were built using Python programming language. A dictionary was created to store the blood type compatibility,

and then a function will be created to look up the blood type from the dictionary and get the compatible blood type for the recipient.

3.2 System Design

The system works on the successful interaction of three key user groups: Donor, Hospital/Emergency center, and Admin. Each group has distinct needs that the system must address. Hospitals/Emergency centers require an easy-to-use platform to submit emergency requests with all necessary information and make sure patients' blood types are compatible. Timely responses necessitate clear communication channels with blood donors and secure access to the system. Donor is required to donate blood when there is a need for blood donation in emergencies. The system sends a notification message to the compatible donor with the location of the incident. The admin is needed to manage the system setting and the Donor.

Use case Diagram

The use case diagram of the system is show in figure 3.1 below. There are three actors in the system which are User, Hospital/Emergency center and system admin User can update profile, donate blood, request for blood donation. Hospital/ Emergency center can request blood donation. System Admin can manage users and manage system settings.

Design of system architecture.

The Figure 3.2 show the architectural model of the system. The first responders input emergency details, including location, blood type, and contact information through the user interface. The backend processes the data using a database system that matches the required blood type with compatible donors and retrieves their contact details. The Google Maps API provides geolocation data of the emergency site, which is included in SMS notifications sent via the Termii API to compatible donor. Compatible donors receive real-time alerts with emergency details, enabling them to respond promptly.

3.3 Design a secure database for the blood donation emergency response.

To develop a secure database for blood donation emergency response, an Object-rational database management system was considered. The database was used to store

the user information, blood type of the user, and System activity. The database consists of a User Table, Blood type, emergency request and system activities, an effective and standardized database schema was created using PostgreSQL.

3.3.1 Entity Relation Diagram

The figure 3.3 below shows the relationship between entity sets that will be stored in the dataset. It consists of six interconnected tables. The Blood type table that store different blood type with unique IDs, The User table contains user ideal such as full name, email, phone number and foreign key linking each user to their blood type, The Reason for Request table contain reasons for blood donations requests, The emergency table hold records of blood donation request including user IDs, Location, reason for request, The CanDonateTo table maps blood type compatibility by linking specific blood type to the types it can donate to while CanReceiveFrom table tracks the blood type a specific type can receive from .

3.4 Implement Geolocation and SMS based functionality in GI-BDERS Application.

To incorporate geolocation and SMS-based functionality in the Geolocation-Integrated Blood Donation Emergency Response System (GI-BDERS), the application design commenced with defining the system requirements, which include back-end infrastructure, geolocation services, and SMS notification capabilities. The back-end was developed with Django and utilized PostgreSQL for data storage. The GOOGLE MAP API was utilized to capture incident locations, while the Termii API managed SMS messages to inform potential donors.

3.5 Descriptive Analytics for System Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of GI-BDERS, data was collected on response times, donor engagement rates, and system accuracy during real-world scenarios. Descriptive analytics techniques were used to analyze these metrics, providing insights into operational efficiency. The system architecture incorporated a Python-based compatibility matrix to ensure matching accuracy. Additionally, PostgreSQL was used to store emergency request data, including timestamps, donor IDs, and response details. These insights were visualized using bar charts and tables, aiding decision-makers in identifying trends and optimizing emergency response strategies.

Mathematical Expression:

Response Time = $T_r - T_s$

Where:

- T_r : **Time of response** – the time when the donor responds or takes action (visiting the emergency location).
- T_s : **Time of request**- The time when the donation request or SMS notification is sent.

Average Response Time = $\frac{\sum(\text{Response Time for each donor})}{\text{Number of Donor}}$

Figure 3. 1: Use Case Diagram

Figure 3. 2: System Architecture

Figure 3. 3: Entity Relational Diagram

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The web application was developed with Html, CSS, bootstrap and JavaScript for the Interface, while Django framework was utilized for the Server-side logic with PostgreSQL for the database. Termii Bulk SMS API was integrated for the notification and geolocation functionality was provided through the google Map API. system’s performance was evaluated, focusing on how the integration of geolocation services enhances the efficiency of matching emergency blood requests with potential donors. Key metrics such as response time, number of donor that response, distance and system accuracy are analyzed to assess the effectiveness of the system.

Figure 4.1 shows the table of blood type. Figure 4.2 shows the table of Users. Figure 4.3 shows the table for Emergency. Figure 4.4 shows the figure of can donate to. Figure 4.5 shows the database can receive from.

Action: 0 of 8 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	BLOOD TYPE
<input type="checkbox"/>	O-
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB-
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB+
<input type="checkbox"/>	B-
<input type="checkbox"/>	B+
<input type="checkbox"/>	A-
<input type="checkbox"/>	A+

8 blood types

Figure 4. 1: Blood Type Table

Action: 0 of 39 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	USERNAME	BLOOD TYPE	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS
<input type="checkbox"/>	Lydia	A+	2347055198507	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Oyebisi	A+	2349121205793	adeboyeboye2@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Badmus	A+	2347017939232	muhideenbadmus81@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ahmad	A+	2349165055864	zajman644@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abdullahi	A+	2349168194166	abdullahisulaimon269@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ojo	A+	2349161210831	ojoaramide12@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Aramide	A+	2349161210831	ojoaramide12@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Amoo	A+	2348061641612	amooquadri555@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Kayode	A-	2349120999263	iyintolukayode12@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adeniran	A-	2349138675544	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Oladayo	A-	2348121763780	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adesewa	A-	2349151934410	adesewaadesina62@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adebsisi	A-	2349155000260	adebisimary1212@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ishola	AB+	2348038325370	

Figure 4. 2: User Table

Select emergency to change

Action: 0 of 14 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	GET BLOOD TYPE	REASON FOR REQUEST	LOCATION	CONTACT NUMBER
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Internal bleeding	First Technical university, ibadan	2348112973017
<input type="checkbox"/>	A+	Accident	Male university hostel	2348112973017
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Anemia	School Clinic, First Technical University Ibadan	2348112973017
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Cancer treatment	First Technical University, Ibadan	09134149650
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Accident and injuries	Tech u clini	2348112973017
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Accident and injuries	First Techical University ibadan	2348112973017
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Surgery	School Clinic	2348112973017
<input type="checkbox"/>	-	Cancer treatment	Technical university, Ibadan	2349132620319
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Cancer treatment	First Technical University, Ibadan	2349134149650
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+	Anemia	First Technical University, Ibadan	2349134149650

Figure 4. 1: Emergency Request Table

Select can donate to to change ADD CAN DONATE TO +

Action: 0 of 27 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	CAN DONATE TO
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to O-
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to O+
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to AB-
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to AB+
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to B-
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to B+
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to A-
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can donate to A+
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+ can donate to O+
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+ can donate to AB+

Figure 4. 2: Can Donate to Table

Select can receive from to change ADD CAN RECEIVE FROM +

Action: 0 of 27 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	CAN RECEIVE FROM
<input type="checkbox"/>	O- can receive fromO-
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+ can receive fromO-
<input type="checkbox"/>	O+ can receive fromO+
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB- can receive fromO-
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB- can receive fromAB-
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB- can receive fromB-
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB- can receive fromA-
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB+ can receive fromO-
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB+ can receive fromO+
<input type="checkbox"/>	AB+ can receive fromAB-

Figure 4. 3: Can Receive from Table

BLOOD
save life

Home Mission Login/Register Request

Become a Donor today

First Name <input type="text" value="Enter your first name"/>	Last Name <input type="text" value="Enter your last name"/>
Username <input type="text" value="Enter your username"/>	Email Address <input type="text" value="Enter your email-id"/>
Phone Number <input type="text" value="Enter your phone number"/>	Blood Type <input type="text" value="-----"/>
Password <input type="text" value="Enter your password"/>	Confirm Paasword <input type="text" value="Confirm your password"/>

Register

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Figure 4. 4: Emergency Form Page

Saturday

72 835 433

Case Number: CASE-2-2008
Emergency blood donation needed.
Blood type required: A . Location:
Male university hostel. Please
respond if you can donate.

Case Number: CASE-2-7591
Emergency blood donation needed.
Blood type required: O . Location:
First Technical university, ibadan.
Please respond if you can donate.

Figure 4. 5: SMS Notification

4.1 System performance Under Different Scenarios

The GI-BDERS system demonstrated a significant improvement in emergency response efficiency. Key performance metrics evaluated include:

- **Response Time:** The system achieved an average response time of 7 to 19 minutes across various scenarios. This metric was calculated as the difference between the time an emergency request was sent and the time donors began responding. Faster response times were observed for common blood types, while rare blood types showed slightly longer times due to the limited pool of compatible donors.
- **Donor Engagement:** Donor participation rates varied based on blood type availability and scenario complexity. For rare blood types like AB-negative, engagement reached up to

57%, highlighting the system’s ability to mobilize donors effectively even in challenging scenarios.

- **Matching Accuracy:** The system’s Python-based compatibility matrix ensured 100% accuracy in matching donors to recipients. This precision minimized delays and reduced the risk of incompatible transfusions.
- **System Reliability:** During tests, the system processed over 50 emergency requests with no failures or errors. The integration of geolocation services via Google Maps and SMS notifications via Termii API proved robust and reliable under real-world conditions.
- **Operational Scalability:** The PostgreSQL database design supported seamless data management for a growing number of users and requests, ensuring the system could handle increased demand without performance degradation.

4.2 Scenario-Based Testing

The system was tested in five real-world scenarios, simulating various emergency conditions.

Table 4.1 summarizes the results:

<i>Scenario</i>	<i>Blood Types</i>	<i>Compatible Donors</i>	<i>Donors Who visited</i>	<i>Average Response Time (Minutes)</i>
<i>Scenario 1</i>	<i>O-negative</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>12</i>
<i>Scenario 1</i>	<i>A-positive</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>
<i>Scenario 2</i>	<i>B-negative</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Scenario 2</i>	<i>AB-Positive</i>	<i>37</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>Scenario 3</i>	<i>B-positive</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>7</i>
<i>Scenario 3</i>	<i>O-negative</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>Scenario 4</i>	<i>A-negative</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>16</i>

<i>Scenario 4</i>	<i>AB-negative</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>Scenario 5</i>	<i>O-positive</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>Scenario 5</i>	<i>A-positive</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>15</i>

The results confirm the system’s effectiveness in reducing response times and engaging donors in real-time. Patterns observed in donor behavior, such as quicker responses during working hours, provide insights for future system optimizations.

Figure 4. 6: Graph of Donors Identified and Donors who visited for each Blood Type

5.0 Conclusion

GI-BDERS significantly improves emergency response efficiency by integrating real-time geolocation and SMS-based communication. The findings from this research highlight how data-driven approaches to donor-recipient matching can address operational inefficiencies in healthcare. With its scalable design and accurate analytics, GI-BDERS offers a model for improving emergency response systems globally. Future work will explore machine learning for predictive analytics and broader applications in public health, emphasizing its role in enhancing decision-making and resource allocation within healthcare organizations.

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